

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D1.2 THIRD TECHNICAL REPORT

PART B

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Glossary

AOP	Advanced Oxidation Process
BU	Boğaziçi Üniversitesi,
CERTE	Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux,
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan,
CRDA	Regional Commissary for Agricultural Development (Tunisia),
D	Deliverable,
DMP	Data Management Plan,
DSI	State Hydraulic Works,
DSS	Decision Support System,
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography,
FIS	Fuzzy Inference System,
HRMA	High-Resolution Monitoring Approach,
HRMS	High-Resolution Monitoring Sensors,
IST-ID	Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento,
MED	Mediterranean,
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats,
TUC	Technical University of Crete,
UFZ	Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung,
UNIPR	Università degli Studi di Parma,
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València,
WTD	Water Table Depth,
WP	Work Package.

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies, including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS), and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The third technical report summarises the work undertaken by the seven scientific teams from Portugal, Spain, Germany, Italy, Tunisia, Greece, and Turkey. The report encompasses the entire project period, starting in March 2020 and concluding in August 2023. The report focuses on the analysis of the objectives of the project and their accomplishments. Furthermore, the report addresses any deviations from the original proposal submitted, explaining their reasons and presenting and discussing the corrective actions taken to address them.

1. Explanation of the Work Carried Out by the Beneficiaries and Overview of the Progress

The third technical report details the work conducted by the seven scientific teams that comprise InTheMED during the entire implementation of the project from March 1, 2020, to August 31, 2023. The specific objectives and the degree of fulfilment of each are analysed, the work carried out by each WP is thoroughly highlighted individually, and the interconnection between the different teams is clearly displayed.

Table 1. List of completed deliverables.

Code	Deliverable Name	WP	Submission date to MEL
D1.1	Consortium Agreement	1	2020/11/13
D1.2	Mid-Term Technical Report	1	2022/02/09
D1.2	Second Technical Report	1	2023/03/31
D1.3	Documentation of Kick-Off, Annual Coordination and WP leader meetings	1	2023/07/26
D1.4	Data Management Plan v1	1	2021/03/03
D1.4	Data Management Plan v2	1	2022/03/31
D1.4	Data Management Plan v3		2023/08/30
D2.1	Report on the Integrated and Innovative High-Resolution Monitoring Strategies in the Different Case Studies	2	2021/08/31
D2.2	Report on the Existing Historical Groundwater Data on the MED Region	2	2022/08/22
D2.3	Report on Regional Groundwater Trends and Their Controlling Factors	2	2023/07/31
D2.4	Reinforcement of the Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing	2	2023/05/05
D3.1	Identification of the Surrogate Models to be Applied in the Case Studies	3	2022/03/31
D3.2	Report on Surrogate Models in the Case Studies	3	2023/07/31
D3.3	Data Archive Containing the Downscaled Climate Projections in the Case Studies	3	2022/10/25
D3.4	Report on the Results of the Analysis of Different Scenarios at the Case Studies	3	2023/07/31
D4.1	Report on the Social-Economic System Characterisation, Stakeholder Mapping and Water Governance for Selected Case Studies	4	2021/08/31
D4.2	Report on the Participatory Systems Mapping and the Conceptual Model	4	2022/03/31

D4.3	Report on the Numeric Simulation Model Including Model Input Files	4	2022/11/28
D4.4	Report on Simulation-Based Scenario Analyses and Policy Design	4	2023/08/15
D5.1	Report on Site Characterisation and Hot Spot Identification	5	2022/04/01
D5.2	Report on the Procedure for the Capacity Building and the Selection of the Main Hot Spots	5	2022/08/29
D5.3a	Report on the Appropriate Innovative Remediation Process Developed	5	2023/02/28
D5.3b	Report on the Results of the Upscaling Recommendations of the Innovative Remediation Processes and Reuse Strategies	5	2023/08/07
D6.1	Report on the Development of the Innovative DSS Tool	6	2022/02/28
D6.2	Report on the Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites	6	2023/02/28
D6.3	Atlas of the Maps Produced Using the DSS	6	2023/08/23
D7.1a	Project Website	7	2021/05/14
D7.1b	Communication and Dissemination Plan	7	2021/04/26
D7.2	Communication and Dissemination Activities	7	2023/08/29
D7.3	Report on Synergies with Groundwater Initiatives in the Euro-MED Region	7	2022/09/28
D7.4	Report on Mid-Term Workshop	7	2022/03/31
D7.5	Report on the InTheMED Final Scientific Conference	7	2023/06/29
D7.6	Exploitation plan	7	2023/08/29

Table 2. List of completed milestones.

Code	Milestone Name	WP
M1.1	Consortium Agreement Drafted	1
M1.2	Kick-off Meeting First, Second and Third Periodic Reports Completed	1
M1.3	Final Data Management Plan	1
M2.1	Knowledge Exchange about each Aquifer and Main Groundwater Issues, Existing Datasets and Further Needed Monitoring in Each Case Study Drafted	2
M2.2	Review of Existing Groundwater Data in the MED Region Conducted	2
M2.3	First Draft of Groundwater Trend Analyses Performed	2
M2.4	Key Recommendation for Reinforcement of Science-Based Management in the MED Region Listed	2
M3.1	Choice of the Typology of the Surrogate Models to be Tested in the Five Study Cases	2
M3.2	Evaluation of the Performance of the Surrogate Models Implemented in the Study Cases	
M3.3	Development Of a Web Repository with The Results of The Climate Change Evaluation	3

M3.4	Application Of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios (Climate And Socio-Economic Changes, Remediation Strategies)	3
M4.1	First Living Lab Guiding Problem Identification and System Characterisation	4
M4.2	Second Living Lab Scrutinising and Refining the Conceptual Model	4
M4.3	Development of the Numerical Model	4
M4.4	Third Living Lab for Building Simulation-Based Scenario Analyses and Policy Design	4
M5.1	Inventory Of Existing Water Resources Degradation Assessment Methodologies for Use in InTheMED Case Study Sites	5
M5.2	Review Of the Procedure for The Capacity Building of Hot Spots And Stakeholders	5
M5.3a	First Draft of The Innovative Remediation Strategies Performed	5
M5.3b	First Draft of The Innovative Remediation Strategies Performed	5
M6.1	Initial DSS Algorithm at An Operational Level	6
M6.2	Preliminary Results of The DSS for the Case Study Sites	6
M6.3	First Draft of The Atlas of Maps	6
M7.1	Project Website Launched Online	7
M7.2	Final Version of The Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) Finished	7
M7.3	Synergies With Other Initiatives in The Euro-MED Region Identified and In Place	7
M7.4	Mid-Term Report Drafted	7
M7.5	Final Conference Report Drafted	7

1.1. Objectives

Pillar 1: Strengthening the Understanding of Groundwater Functioning and Trends

OBJ-P1-1 Identification of the Most Important Groundwater Problems in the MED Region

Throughout the project, all partners were involved in identifying groundwater problems through various means, including bibliographic review, SWOT analyses, field visits, interviews with key informants, and workshops with stakeholders. Additionally, a database of over 14,400 piezometers from Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, France, Tunisia, and Turkey was constructed.

It was identified that overexploitation, climate-change threats, and anthropogenic stress lead to groundwater level decline in Grombalia, Requena-Utiel, and Konya. Tympaki faces seawater intrusion, while Castro-Verde, Grombalia, and Tympaki also suffer from aquifer contamination. Furthermore, the project revealed issues beyond groundwater quality and quantity. Problems with monitoring infrastructure and institutional arrangements were identified, such as a lack

of data sharing among most countries, scarcity of long-term groundwater abstraction rates data, limited access to groundwater level data hindering transparency and public participation, unequal economic and institutional capacities for sustainable groundwater management, and the absence of groundwater monitoring standards and a data dictionary among MED countries.

OBJ-P1-2 Investigation of the Long-Term Groundwater Trends

Data from the entire MED region, specifically Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, France, Tunisia and Turkey, were collected and processed. The availability of time series and required data processing was very contrasting for each country. No significant overall trends were found when analysing the most complete time series in the MED region. However, over 20% of the time series indicated a substantial decline in groundwater levels over the years. Looking at specific decades, between 1985 and 1994, over 23% of the selected wells showed a declining trend. In contrast, for the decade between 2005 and 2014, only 13% of the wells exhibited a declining trend, suggesting a possible recovery across the MED region.

To analyse disparities in decadal trends, time series were categorised into clusters based on groundwater dynamics variables and trend results from the 1985-2014 period. These clusters formed nine distinct groups, which can be broadly categorised into three types: those exhibiting mostly stable behaviour, those displaying periods of depletion, and those showing water gain or recovery from depletion.

To better understand the divergent evolutions, driving factors were examined. Stable clusters were associated with highly productive aquifers, temperate climates with consistent year-round precipitation, higher average rainfall, and being further away from irrigation areas compared to other clusters. In contrast, declining wells were linked to arid climates, moderately productive aquifers, and proximity to irrigation areas. Rising wells were primarily connected to higher rates of precipitation increase across the three decades and located at a distance from urban areas.

OBJ-P1-3 Application and Taking Benefits of the Innovative High-Resolution Monitoring Approach (HRMA: Allowing Near Real-Time Monitoring) at the Five Case Studies

In the Tympaki basin, the Water Directorate of Crete has installed two high-resolution sensors, monitoring at 30-minute intervals. The TUC is enabled with full access to sensors' data since there is a strong collaboration between the two institutions. The first one monitors groundwater quantity in the centre of the basin. The second one monitors electrical conductivity to assess saltwater intrusion in the coastal part of the basin. Furthermore, at least three geophysical surveys have been carried out since 2005 to identify the detailed spatial hydrogeological background of the area and the groundwater status. The specific high-resolution data were used to calibrate and validate the numerical and the surrogate groundwater model developed for the study area.

Furthermore, a database was developed to host hydrometeorological data from the wider area of Greece. This database can use the monitoring data collected using the HRMA and contribute to their efficient processing, visualisation and management. A novel geostatistical geo-modelling workflow was also developed for the Tympaki aquifer (Greece). This action was performed jointly by IST-ID and UTC teams by combining geostatistical simulation and Bayesian model averaging.

In the Grombalia site, three AquaTROLL-500 High-Resolution Monitoring Sensors (HRMS) were installed, under the scope of the InTheMED project at hotspot points linked to industrial activities like agri-food, textile, and leather industries, which were suspected to be highly contaminated. The HRMS provide real-time measurements of temperature, nitrate concentrations, and water depth, and they are synchronised with an online remote platform exclusively accessible to the CERTE team. This advanced monitoring system allows for detecting fleeting events that may go unnoticed by the low-frequency sampling of conventional monitoring systems.

In the Konya basin, 122 HRMS were installed by the State Hydraulic Works (DSI) in 122 wells of the Konya Closed basin as part of the national groundwater monitoring network upgrade. These wells are equipped with DCX-22 series sensors manufactured by Keller Inc., enabling temperature, water level, and electrical conductivity measurements at 10-minute intervals. DSI gave the BU team access to the data of 5 HRMS. The data from three monitoring locations (Aksaray, Çumra, and Karapınar) reveal similar patterns, with groundwater levels dropping during intensive irrigation periods and partially recovering in the wet winter seasons. High

groundwater extraction periods increase electrical conductivity and temperature, potentially affecting crop yields.

HRMS were not installed in Castro-Verde (Portugal) due to the lack of communication and engagement with the owner of the mining site. However, an innovative geostatistical ERT inversion method, developed and implemented under the scope of the InTheMED project, was applied to the Castro Verde (Portugal) data set. This data set includes sixty-three two-dimensional ERT profiles within the mining premises. Also, a deep-learning-based (i.e., variational auto-encoders) method for ERT inversion was developed and applied to key ERT sections from the Castro Verde (Portugal) site. Despite the limited communication of the IST-ID team with the mining company, these results were shared with them. UNIPR and IST-ID teams are developing geophysical monitoring for complex groundwater systems in a pilot case using a sandbox. These activities were not initially planned in the project proposal.

HRMS were not installed in Requena-Utiel either. Although the UPV team has worked closely with the Jucar Basin Water Authority, responsible for the Requena-Utiel aquifer management, the Water Authority discouraged the installation of these HRMS on the basis that they are performing a thorough modernisation of the current observation network; unfortunately, while this modernisation has been started, they were not fully operational during the life of the project and could not be used.

Pillar 2: Improvement of Groundwater Resilience and Security in a Social Learning Process

OBJ-P2-1 Incorporating Groundwater Management Within a Broader Socio-Economic Context to Improve Water Resources Resilience Through Stakeholder Workshops and Dynamic Simulation Modelling

Adopting the group model-building approach, three participatory modelling workshops (September 30, 2021, February 17, 2022, and March 21, 2023) were organised in Konya, Turkey. Subsequently, the researchers developed the seed model generated in the workshops. This model aims to simulate the behaviour of key variables within the socio-economic system over time and analyse their response to potential agricultural and groundwater-related policies and environmental scenarios.

OBJ-P2-2 Raising Awareness in Society and Among Concerned Stakeholders to Improve Groundwater Management through the Implementation of a Multi-Actor Participatory Approach in the Selected Case Studies in the MED Region

Three participatory modelling workshops (September 30, 2021, February 17, 2022, and March 21, 2023) were organised in Konya, Turkey, to bring various stakeholder groups together to discuss groundwater-related issues and potential leverage points in the system to improve groundwater management. Four events with a multi-actor participatory approach were organised in Requena, Spain, in collaboration with the Spanish team of the PRIMA eGROUNDWATER project. These events included one living lab (March 4, 2022) and three workshops with concerned stakeholders to analyse groundwater unsustainability in the region and brainstorm possible measures, technological needs, and the design of tools.

OBJ-P2-3 Identification of Groundwater Problems and Implementation of the Appropriate Feasible Preventive Mitigation Options through Sustainable Learning Processes

The surveys mentioned in OPB-P1-1 allow us to know the primary water users and contaminants and evaluate the remediation strategies. Workshops, roundtables, and technical training sessions were organised in Grombalia, Tunisia, to enhance sustainable integrated water management capacity-building. These social and technical learning spaces aim to drive stakeholder understanding of achievable preventative mitigation alternatives and viable remediation options. In Grombalia, Tunisia, at the laboratory scale, an innovative and cost-effective technical solution for industrial textile activity has been developed and optimised based on an advanced oxidation process (AOP) promoting treated wastewater reuse possibilities. In Castro Verde, Portugal, enhancing the real-time monitoring network for groundwater is suggested in terms of quantity and quality.

Additionally, the adoption of new treatment technologies in the mining industry is proposed. In Requena-Utiel, Spain, an innovative smart model has been created to assist stakeholders and managers in evaluating the impact of groundwater extraction in the context of climate change. No changes in the type of irrigation have been proposed because, during the workshops in Requena, farmers commented that they already use very efficient irrigation procedures (mostly drip irrigation). However, it is encouraged to continue along the path of precision agriculture and a reduction in pumping is advised; crop shifting to more profitable, less intensive wine production is also recommended. Likewise, it is necessary to modernise the

groundwater control networks of the Júcar Water Authority. In Tympaki, Greece, an optimised pumping scheme has been designed to maintain the water table at a level that can prevent saltwater intrusion. In Konya, Turkey, three workshops with stakeholders were organised. These are parts of an ongoing social learning process, a living lab, in which participants are encouraged to discover causal relationships within the system and analyse proposed policy options in terms of their effectiveness. Moreover, a seed model has been developed to project the long-term consequences of proposed policy scenarios. The model was shared with the participants through a user-friendly interface to communicate the model findings with the public in a simple, easy-to-understand manner. Both the interface for hosting the dynamic model and tutorials on how to use it, available in both English and Turkish, have been published on the official InTheMED webpage (https://bit.ly/InTheMED_DynamicModel).

Pillar 3: Development of Sustainable Management and Remediation Strategies

OBJ-P3-1 Establishment of Adaptable and Sustainable Management Strategies Through the Combination of HRMA, Tailored Model Results, Socio-Economic Assessments, Bottom-Up Management and Remediation Strategies, an Innovative Fuzzy WebDSS Tool, and Effective Communication Dissemination Strategies

A monitoring scheme was suggested to manage groundwater quantity and quality for each case study. This new monitoring strategy combined grab-sampling (biweekly) and HRMA (very tight measures: sampling interval lower than one hour). In three case studies (Tympaki, Grombalia, and Konya), HRMA were successfully used to improve the existing database and to fill the gap of missing and accurate data. Their results are already contributing to their sustainable management (WP2). The local authority in the region of Grombalia (Tunisia) has been informed about the acquired data from November 2021 up to now, helping them to detect the drying up of a monitoring well and to identify a significant decline in the water table and water quality.

Smart and simplified models for the five case studies were developed for various scenarios considering climatic conditions, land uses, and applied pumping rates. These models have proven to be accessible and innovative tools ready to help with management strategies for the study cases (WP3).

A dynamic simulation model is built for the scenario-based socio-economic assessment of management strategies with stakeholder involvement. The model is aimed to serve as a learning environment when used for policy analysis with large stakeholder participation (WP4). It is accessible through the official InTheMED webpage (https://bit.ly/InTheMED_DynamicModel).

Starting with industrial activities components and building up to the larger system, the CERTE team has developed a bottom-up remediation approach in the Grombalia case study using multi-criteria decision assessment and a statistical inference analysis to predict the cumulative impact of the various practices at the aquifer scale. In addition, innovative remediation strategies were recommended for all case studies (WP5).

The DSS was developed and published online at the official InTheMED webpage (https://bit.ly/InTheMEDWeb_DSS), and it will enable not only the visualisation of the results for each scenario previously defined in the smart modelling but also the comparison of the results among alternative scenarios (WP6).

These activities were effective and actively communicated and disseminated with all relevant stakeholders through virtual brochures, posters and factsheets, peer-reviewed papers, and oral presentations in conferences, webpages, and social media (WP7).

OBJ-P3-2 Prediction of the Effects of Future Climate and Anthropogenic Changes and How They Can Be Mitigated by Stakeholder-Suggested Preventive Options Using Smart Modelling

Smart models were created to explore various climate and socio-economic scenarios. To obtain reliable future climate data that can be used as input to the smart models, future projections obtained from an ensemble of 17 EURO-CORDEX climate models under two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) were provided. As a result, a data repository containing the future climate data downscaled and bias corrected at the case-study scale was created. This repository serves as input for the smart models, enabling an assessment of the impact of climate change on groundwater resources with its associated uncertainties. In addition, a dynamic simulation model for Konya, Turkey, was developed to analyse the behaviour of crucial system variables under different environmental scenarios and policy choices in the medium term. Preventive

options include raising stakeholder awareness to strengthen state efforts in managing local water resources and providing technical support during remediation strategy implementation.

OBJ-P3-3 Advice to the Most Polluting Industries at Selected Sites to Reduce their Discharge Loads Through the Adoption of a Local Water Management Concept and the Implementation of the Best Available Technologies in the Market for the Appropriate Treatment of Their Effluents

Polluting industries were identified only at the Grombalia and Castro Verde sites. The abrupt cease of communications with the property of the mine connected to the Castro Verda aquifer prevented us from advising the mine owners, but in the Grombalia aquifer, the industrial sector was more receptive.

Two actions are proposed to accelerate the reduction of contamination by the industrial sector in the Grombalia aquifer:

- Implementation of a cost-effective electrochemical treatment process in identified industrial hotspots, such as the textile sector (68 industries). This innovative approach will help decrease the discharge of organic and inorganic contaminants into the environment and water bodies. It also supports clean industrial production, aligning with water reuse standards and the circular economy.
- Improvement of data-driven aquifer monitoring through the use of HRMS sensors and foster collaboration with national decision-makers. This entails sharing collected data and expanding the monitoring network. Additionally, capacity building on technical aspects of sustainable and integrated water management will be emphasised.

Pillar 4: Reinforcement of the DSS, Communication and Dissemination Activities

OBJ-P4-1 Development of an Innovative and Easy-To-Use Fuzzy WebDSS Tool Benefiting from the Real-Time Measured Data Using Specific Sensors and Modelling Results to Reinforce Early-Warning and Ensure the Real-Time Groundwater Characterization and Optimal Decision Making

The DSS tool is accessible to any interested user via the internet (https://bit.ly/InTheMEDWeb_DSS). The tool allows end users to query the smart model easily and visualise the results according to their input parameters. In addition, end users can compare two scenarios (e.g., current and future conditions) for the same case study site in a

split screen. For these two user-defined scenarios, hydraulic head results are processed using the Fuzzy Clustering Method to identify impacted areas based on the user's input and sort these areas into classes based on the variation in groundwater levels. The tool benefits from in situ data, climate change models, and surrogate models incorporating spatial and temporal variations.

OBJ-P4-2 Promotion of InTheMED Results and Improvement of its Regional and International Visibility through the Participation in High-Level International Conferences, Reinforcement of Open Data Access – Opting in the Pilot Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 – and Integration of Different Initiatives Targeting the MED Region

Twelve peer-reviewed papers were published in international journals, and 44 communications at several international scientific conferences were delivered throughout the entire implementation of the project. Multiple workshops, living labs and training sessions were organised with relevant stakeholders from the different case studies. Also, exhibitions and dissemination sessions were planned related to sustainable groundwater management and to disseminate the results of InTheMED to the general public. Efforts were also developed to link InTheMED with other MED initiatives. In Grombalia, Tunisia, there is an ongoing collaboration with the A-RESET project (help for water sector reforms in Tunisia), which is being carried out with the technical assistance of the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) and was developed by the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture. InTheMED actively collaborated with other PRIMA-funded projects, Sustain-COAST¹, GOTHAM², and eGROUNDWATER³.

InTheMED results are shared through the project data repository at ZENODO⁴ and the project website⁵ under FAIR principles and following the project Data Management Plan guidelines.

OBJ-P4-3 Upscaling of the InTheMED Concept to the Whole MED Region and Replicability of its Methodology to other MED Countries through Cross-Country Dissemination Tools Based on Participatory Workshops and Public Communication

¹ <https://www.sustain-coast.tuc.gr/>

² <https://web.archive.org/web/20230712013050/https://www.gotham-prima.eu/>

³ <https://egroundwater.com/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/inthemed/>

⁵ <https://inthemedprima.com/>

All scientific teams investigated solutions that could be replicable and transferable to other case studies in the MED region and applied them to the five case studies. The participatory workshops with agents from the MED region were held to strengthen links with other international research projects related to sustainable groundwater management. InTheMED promoted the webinar 'Groundwater: facing a common challenge 2022' between several PRIMA Projects and held an EGU 2023 session ('EGU session - HS8.1.9, Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions') dedicated to sustainable groundwater management focused on the results of the project. In Grombalia, Tunisia, the upscaling task is intended to work in consonance with ongoing projects in the region, particularly the A-RESET project (help for water sector reforms in Tunisia), which is being carried out with the technical assistance of the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) and was developed by the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture. The industrial sector of the Grombalia River basin is assisted under this project's framework to improve integrated and sustainable water resource management. The InTheMED project team contributes to reinforcing and supporting the project's efforts.

1.2.Explanation of the Work Carried per WP

1.2.1. WP1: Innovative Project Management

The UPV team, being the Project Coordinator and WP1 leader, completed tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4 and played a crucial role in fostering active and efficient participation among all project participants. They created the necessary document templates so that all documents kept a coherent and representative format for the InTheMED project. UPV team reviewed all deliverables to ensure scientific consistency and compliance with the InTheMED design format and DMP provisions. Moreover, they were responsible for controlling the work progress by sending timely reminders and uploading documents to the MEL web platform. Each team contributed to the seamless execution and management of the project at the national level, encompassing financial, administrative and scientific aspects, facilitating the integral management of the project.

During the first year and a half of the InTheMED project and due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, meetings had to be online. From the year 2022, we began to hold in-person meetings. In addition to the frequent virtual meetings, these are the main meetings that we organised:

- Kick-off meeting: April 28, 2020.
- Project Management Board Meeting: May 6, 2020.
- Steering Committee Meetings: October 7, 2020, and May 15, 2021.
- Scientific Advisory Meeting: April 12, 2021, with the presence of Andrés Sahuquillo, Daoud Slim, Encarnación Taguas, Gerald Corzo and Pier Paolo Roggero as the members of the InTheMED Advisory Board.
- First InTheMED Annual Meeting: September 16 and 17, 2021.
- InTheMED Midterm meeting: March 22 – 24, 2022, in Valencia (Spain).
- Second InTheMED Annual Meeting: September 12 and 13, 2022, in Chania (Greece).
- InTheMED Progress Meeting: April 26, 2023, in Vienna (Austria).
- InTheMED Final Meeting: July 11 and 12, 2023, in Istanbul (Turkey).

1.2.2. WP2: Innovative Monitoring and Data Analysis in the MED

The UFZ team, WP2 leader, successfully completed tasks 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4. During the project's three and a half years, significant progress has been made in various aspects related to groundwater monitoring and historical data collection and analysis in the MED region.

Regarding Task 2.1 “Implementation of an Innovative High-Resolution Monitoring”, a comprehensive strategy for implementing HRMA in the study cases was developed, and its benefits were presented to partner countries, along with guidance on equipment selection for specific monitoring objectives.

Concerning Task 2.2, “Review and Collect the Available Groundwater Quantity and Quality Data Sets in the MED Region”, efforts have been dedicated to building the most comprehensive and historical in-situ groundwater level time series database for Mediterranean countries. For the first time, data from diverse sources were obtained, processed, and structured into a common format. However, challenges related to access, measuring frequencies, completeness, data sharing policies, language barriers and the COVID-19 pandemic slowed the process at the beginning of the project. Historical groundwater level time series data were collected from

14,400 piezometers from Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece, Turkey and Tunisia. Groundwater quality data collection was mostly through literature review, as challenges with availability and completeness persist.

For Task 2.3, “Regional Groundwater Trends and Trajectories Analyses and Their Controlling Factors Using SMART Indicators”, groundwater level trends were assessed for piezometers with at least ten years of data from the countries with the most data processing, Spain, Portugal, Italy and France. A total of 5,638 piezometers were assessed at first. Man Kendall (MK) based methods were used to identify the one that best fits the annual means of Water Table Depth (WTD) conditions. A range of analyses were made for different periods, looking for more complete time series data. To analyse the controlling factors of the time series, they have been grouped and analysed with different variables related to groundwater dynamics. Furthermore, the influence of climate type, precipitation, evapotranspiration, and geological variables on these temporal evolutions has been investigated.

As for Task 2.4, “Reinforcement of the Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing in the MED Region”, and towards science-based groundwater management, recommendations and best practices were developed to reinforce systematic monitoring and data sharing in the study cases and the Mediterranean region at large. A review of the current state, challenges, and monitoring system goals can inform specific improvement opportunities. Additionally, analyses from other WPs will help identify areas where groundwater monitoring infrastructure or schemes need installation, modification, or extension to enhance sustainable groundwater management.

Finally, the IST-ID team applied the geostatistical ERT inversion methodology to Castro Verde (Portugal), developed a deep learning ERT inversion methodology and, in collaboration with the TUC team, applied the geostatistical methodology combining stochastic sequential simulation and Bayesian model averaging to model the spatial distribution of the saltwater intrusion in the Tympaki Basin (Crete). Using a sandbox, IST-ID and UNIPR developed a geophysical monitoring system at the lab scale.

1.2.3. WP3: Innovative Smart Modelling in the MED

The UNIPR team, WP3 leader, completed tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. WP3 aims to address the challenges posed by climate and socio-economic scenarios in the five study cases by implementing smart models. To accomplish Task 3.1, “Selection of the Smart Model Types Suitable for Application to Groundwater Systems”, the UNIPR team carried out a detailed literature review and application examples were developed in collaboration with the rest of the partners. And then, Task 3.2, “Training and Validation of the Models in the Case Studies”, was fulfilled. For Requena-Utiel (Spain), Konya (Turkey) and Tympaki (Greece) pilot sites, surrogate models were developed based on the results of complete numerical models, which allow to account for both climate and socio-economic scenarios. In particular, random forest and artificial neural network algorithms were used for the first two case studies, respectively, while the third one employed a spatiotemporal geostatistical model. For Grombalia (Tunisia) and Guadiana basin (Portugal), where complete numerical models were unavailable, the surrogate models were developed using historical information. For these last two cases, a simple statistical approach that relies on regression models was developed to evaluate the impact of future climate scenarios on groundwater resources.

With Task 3.3, “Downscaling of Future Climate Projections at the Case-Study Scale and Their Transfer to the Partners”, reliable future climate data are obtained to be used as input to the smart models. The future projections obtained from an ensemble of 17 EURO-CORDEX climate models under two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) were provided. As a result, a data repository containing the future climate data downscaled and bias corrected at the case-study scale was created.

As for Task 3.4, “Analysis of Different Scenarios”, the final objective of WP3 was to define the scenarios to be explored and present the corresponding outcomes. The scenarios were tailored to each case study according to climatic projections, local regulations, social conditions, crop demand, and average use, depending on the study case. The findings revealed a widespread decline in groundwater levels across most sites under consideration due to the combination of overexploitation and climate change. These results are valuable for stakeholders as they can evaluate different situations and potential scenarios involving climate and socio-economic changes. Smart models are also integrated into the DSS to expedite the decision-making process in the pilot sites.

Furthermore, the TUC team developed a novel laboratory-scale method to comprehend the interaction between soil particles and nanoparticles. This pioneering work not only benefits the Tympaki aquifer but also has broader applications on a national and international scale.

1.2.4. WP4: Innovative Governance and Socio-Economic Assessment in the MED

The BU team, WP4 leader, completed Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4. Regarding Task 4.1, “Systems Characterization, Stakeholder Mapping and Governance Analysis”, a detailed literature review has been conducted to familiarise BU, UPV and CERTE teams with their local and national groundwater policies, stakeholders and main groundwater-related issues in Konya (Turkey), Requena-Utiel (Spain), and Grombalia (Tunisia), respectively. Then, stakeholders and missing information were identified. The BU team created a semi-structured questionnaire template to close the information gap and get to know the stakeholders. This template was translated into the local languages of the case studies to serve as guidance material for interviews with stakeholders involved in each area of study. From March to October 2021, BU, UPV, and CERTE teams organised various field trips, and each team conducted interviews with relevant stakeholders. Thanks to these interviews, the participants in the workshops were selected.

For Task 4.2, “Participatory Systems Mapping and Conceptual Modelling”, Task 4.3 “, Numerical Model Building”, and Task 4.4 “, Scenario Analysis and Policy Design”, the BU team worked on the socio-economic assessment of Konya, Turkey, and for that, they organised three workshops and performed the following activities. The first workshop of the living lab was organised on September 30, 2021, with 26 participants from 14 institutions. It aimed to build trust between the research team and the stakeholders and to build consensus on the problem definition. The second workshop of the living lab was organised on February 17, 2022, with 20 participants from 10 institutions. This workshop's objective was to build a seed model to be used as a basis for the socio-economic assessment. The BU team developed a dynamic simulation model for the Konya aquifer (Turkey), including relevant aspects of the system, feeding from the discussions in the first and second workshops. A field trip was organised on January 15-18, 2023, to share initial model results with prominent stakeholders in the field and validate the model behaviour. The third and final workshop of the Living Lab was conducted on March 21, 2023. This workshop focused on communicating the model results with the

stakeholders and discussing potential policy alternatives and their consequences. To that end, the research team organised seven meetings with selected stakeholders.

The UPV team actively engaged in stakeholder interviews involving six irrigation communities, two municipalities, one industrial groundwater user (bottling company), and one individual groundwater user (winery). With a focus on innovative governance and assessing the socio-economic context of the Requena-Utiel aquifer, the UPV team collaborated with the Spanish team of the PRIMA-funded eGROUNDWATER project to organise four events. These events included one living lab conducted on March 4, 2022, and three workshops, providing valuable opportunities for knowledge exchange, brainstorming, and collaborative discussions among stakeholders.

1.2.5. WP5: Innovative Remediation Strategies in the MED

The CERTE team led WP5 and achieved the three tasks, 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. Concerning Task 5.1, “Site Characterization and Hotspot Identification”, each team provided a comprehensive analysis of each case study site and information on the management structure of the water sector of each partner country from the national to the local level. Also, the five case studies were investigated through a detailed SWOT analysis, which was very useful to support the work carried out in WP2, analysing the main groundwater problems in the MED, in WP3, defining the variables of interest for each case study for the development of intelligent smart models and in WP4, mapping the stakeholders.

Regarding Task 5.2, “Capacity Building on Sustainable Integrated Water Management”, the stakeholders were selected regarding the outputs and main issues identified in Task 5.1. In this context, the CERTE team organised an intensive capacity-building session for professionals working in the field of textile industry in Grombalia to support them in designing and implementing new water-related approaches on integrated local wastewater management and reuse. For this purpose, new and creative techniques in electrochemistry have been applied to address the issue of textile wastewater treatment in Grombalia. Throughout the process, various assessments were carried out to evaluate water quality. A comparative analysis revealed cost solutions that outperformed the industrial methods. The laboratory research provided insights into selecting treatment technologies capable of eliminating recalcitrant contaminants. The main results have been presented to the chosen textile industry

in dedicated training sessions. Additionally, the scalability of these methods was assessed for their application in the agri-food and leather industries. Furthermore, the CERTE team elaborated a survey to acquire information regarding each case study's principal and specific problems, and the teams corresponding to each case study (IST-ID, UPV, BU, and TUC) filled it out.

In relation to Task 5.3a, “Development of water remediation technologies and strategies”, the CERTE team refined a sustainable remediation strategy for the Grombalia case study to overcome the water resource challenges related to the industrial textile sector based on an active engagement of local stakeholders to enhance tailored and local decentralised water management for the reduction of industrial pollution. Based on the specific characteristics of the water quality requirements used in the different steps of the process, various innovative wastewater treatment alternatives, basically electrochemical techniques, were developed and tested for the textile industries. Several sampling campaigns were accomplished to assess the water quality during the industrial process. A comparative investigation, referring to the in-situ industrial process, was assessed, underlining the cost-effective outputs of each option. The adoption of the most suitable technologies for wastewater treatment was reinforced by intensive laboratory-scale research investigations to remove the most recalcitrant and highly toxic emergent contaminants to ensure the safe reuse of the treated effluents. For the rest of the case studies, the corresponding team (IST-ID, UPV, BU, and TUC) proposed adequate remediation actions to be adopted to overcome the problems and issues related to each case study.

The activities of upscaling the proposed remediation technologies were tested, and two other industrial activities were assessed: agri-food and leather.

As part of Task 5.3.b, “Upscaling and implementation of remediation technologies and strategies”, the InTheMED project has collaborated with the A-RESET project, titled "Supporting Water Sector Reforms in Tunisia" which is a national initiative launched by the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP) and financially supported by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ), with technical assistance from GIZ (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit), specifically through the component called "Accompanying territorial actors for an integrated

approach to the sustainable management of water resources in the industrial sector." This component is being implemented by CITET (Tunis International Centre for Environmental Technologies). The main objective of this intervention is to establish a collaborative partnership among various stakeholders and foster a collective approach to sustainably managing water resources in the industrial sector, particularly focusing on alleviating the pressure on the Grombalia aquifer resources. The CERTE team plays a significant role in this ongoing process by providing technical support to local stakeholders in devising a remediation strategy mainly focused on the industrial sector. This assistance is based on the expertise acquired from the project and the successful practices developed at a specific sectoral level.

Also, specific recommendations and guidance on upscaling methodology to better overcome the identified problems were suggested in each case study: (i) suggestions of optimum pumping scheme and rates and best water resources management in Konya (Turkey) as well as in Tympaki (Greece), (ii) recommendations on best hydrogeological model and monitoring network in Castro Verde (Portugal) in addition to guidance in wastewater treatment and water recycling seed models to avoid excessive groundwater salinisation issues related to the used water quality for irrigation, (iii) recommendation for smart modelling use and networks control and proposition of a water balance approach in Requena-Utiel (Spain), and finally (iv) estimation of industrial cumulative pollution effects at the watershed scale of Grombalia (Tunisia) using a statistical approach based on Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis and recommendations on codesigning remediation strategies in the MED region.

1.2.6. WP6: Innovative Decision Support Systems in the MED

The TUC team led WP6 and completed tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3. As part of Task 6.1, "Initial Development and Testing of an Innovative Decision Support System", the TUC team conducted literature research, created a questionnaire to aid the implementation of the decision support steps, which was answered by the teams of each case study, developed a cost-benefit analysis for Tympaki, Requena-Utiel, and Konya case studies and a simulation-optimisation approach for Tympaki, tested several alternatives of DSS methods for the Tympaki aquifer, and finally implemented the web-based Fuzzy DSS tool for all the case study sites. The development of the web-based Fuzzy DSS tool benefits from the surrogate models, and their ability to perform faster simulation runs is based on climate and groundwater use data. A database was also

developed that contains hydrometeorological data from all available stations for the Tympaki case study and the entire island of Crete, contributing to their efficient management and visualisation.

For Task 6.2, “Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites under Future Scenarios”, the TUC team applied the cost-benefit analysis based on the data collected and the defined climate projections for each study case. The proposed water resources distribution indicates an increase in groundwater use for the climate projections until 2031 compared to the historical data, while for the climate projections until 2041, the proposed groundwater use presents a slight decrease or remains the same. Especially for the Tympaki study site, the proposed groundwater use for 2041 was considered in applying groundwater optimisation and optimum results were determined for the different climate projections. Simulation results based on the optimum pumping rates indicate that saltwater intrusion can be retained and ameliorated. These results are helpful to the decision-makers during groundwater use licensing and for the design of new infrastructure.

Concerning Task 6.3, the "Atlas of Groundwater Level Maps" stands as a transformative milestone in sustainable groundwater management, offering a holistic approach to address the pressing challenges faced by the Mediterranean region. This innovative atlas provides the potential of the Decision Support System (DSS) platform driven by fuzzy logic, which was developed to fulfil the aim and scope of the InTheMED project, offering a comprehensive and user-friendly platform for stakeholders engaged in groundwater management. The Atlas of Maps is the output of the DSS platform, providing a series of groundwater variation maps based on the management scenarios suggested as good practice in each study area. This atlas is more than a collection of maps; it demonstrates our commitment to responsible stewardship. By leveraging the power of DSS, we not only interpret the complexities of groundwater systems but also provide a path toward a sustainable and resilient Mediterranean water future.

The UPV, BU and UNIPR teams responded to all the questionnaires and surveys. They were responsible for preparing the files for the Requena-Utiel, Guadiana Basin, Grombalia and Konya case studies to ensure the seamless integration of the smart models into the Decision Support System.

1.2.7. WP7: Innovative Dissemination and Communication in the MED

The IST-ID team led WP7 and completed tasks 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5 and 7.6. Regarding Task 7.1, “Innovative Communication and Dissemination Plan”, the InTheMED website⁶ was released to the public at month six into the project. The Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) was finalised with contributions from all partners. The IST-ID team has frequently updated the project's website and has been the main hub for the InTheMED community to share relevant news about the project. The CDP consolidates the communication and dissemination strategy of the InTheMED project, identifies the most efficient means to communicate with partners and stakeholders and disseminates, exploits and communicates the results. The CDP sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited to effectively spread InTheMED activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences and relevant stakeholders. It includes the official logo of the project and the visual identity built around the main logo. One of the components of the CDP was the creation of a virtual identity and the presence of the project on social media channels. This objective was accomplished by creating Twitter⁷, LinkedIn⁸, Facebook⁹, and YouTube¹⁰ user accounts. These platforms are regularly updated with information related to the project.

As part of Task 7.2, “Innovative Communication and Dissemination Activities”, project members actively promoted the InTheMED project and its results. These efforts included disseminating the project through news on institutional websites and participating in workshops, exhibitions and dissemination sessions. Twelve peer-reviewed papers were published in international journals, and 44 oral communications at several international scientific conferences were delivered.

For Task 7.3, “Synergies with Other MED Initiatives and Projects”, an effort has been made to interact with accounts from other PRIMA projects. A few webinars were organised in collaboration with three other PRIMA-funded projects: GOTHAM, RESERVOIR and eGROUNDWATER. There has been a regular interaction with Sustain-COAST, MEDSAL and

⁶ <https://inthemedprima.com/>

⁷ https://twitter.com/inthemed_prima

⁸ <https://pt.linkedin.com/in/inthemed-prima-5690461ba>

⁹ <https://m.facebook.com/inthemedPRIMA/>

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/@projectinthemed4258>

eGROUNDWATER PRIMA projects, leading to several joint publications and, with the latter project, the organisation of workshops.

Task 7.4, “InTheMED Mid-Term Workshop”, was organised by the UPV team and took place at UPV, Spain, from March 22 to March 24, 2022. In this workshop, each partner did an update about the status of each WP, did a presentation on a non-related topic to spark new collaboration initiatives and a half-day was devoted to a mock-up of a Living Lab promoted by the BU team.

Task 7.5 “InTheMED Final Scientific Conference” took place at the EGU (European Geosciences Union) General Assembly 2023 in Vienna (Austria) from April 23 to April 28, 2023, in a special session dedicated to the presentation of the project's results. The final conference was held on the last day, where there was the opportunity for the partners to present their results obtained under the project framework in a well-attended session that attracted presentations from elsewhere.

Task 7.6 “InTheMED Exploitation Plan” summarises key exploitable results and the strategies and modes the InTheMED consortium plans for the creation of impact and the potential upscaling of the innovative management and modelling tools developed under the scope of the project to other regions of the world. Preparation for exploitation was co-developed with all consortium partners and reflected the interactions with the relevant stakeholders for each case study.

2. Impacts

As stated in the project proposal for all WPs, the expected impacts are relevant, and all the proposed objectives were successfully achieved, as detailed above.

3. Deviations from the Proposal Submitted

From the beginning of the project, a delay was predicted in most tasks due to the extraordinary situation caused by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. During this first year and a half, meetings with third-party agents and stakeholders have been postponed or cancelled due to lockdowns and travel restrictions measures. Additionally, it was impossible to carry out fieldwork, sampling campaigns and installation of new sensors. The universities, research centres and water authorities have adopted severe measures that have made certain processes lengthy, such as hiring personnel and buying equipment. Most tasks have suffered a 6-month deviation from the project plan, as reflected by the Gantt chart submitted in the proposal. After receiving a positive midterm evaluation and the approval of the first periodic report, InTheMED was granted an extension of six months, delaying the final date of the project to August 31, 2023. Apart from the initial delay, there have been no substantial delays in the tasks concerning the final schedule.

3.1. Tasks

Task 2.1: Implementation of an Innovative High-Resolution Monitoring

Installing HRMS in Requena-Utiel (Spain) was impossible for two reasons. Firstly, the Júcar Water Authority had plans to renew the entire monitoring network with high-frequency sensors, but as of now, the data from these sensors are unavailable, and some sensors are yet to be installed. Secondly, the Júcar Water Authority provided a couple of boreholes they no longer intended to monitor, suggesting the option to install our sensors. However, upon inspection, it was concluded that the installation of sensors was not feasible.

In Castro Verde (Portugal), installing the HRMS was impossible due to a lack of communication with the owner of the mining site where the aquifer is located. Therefore, in Castro Verde, only geophysical data was used.

Initially, it was planned to install three HRMS in the Konya Closed Basin. However, after field works and contacts with the State Hydraulic Works of Turkey (DSI), it was revealed that no free secure wells were available for installing InTheMED sensors. Moreover, finding a secure farm in the basin was challenging for that purpose. Instead, the DSI proposed that they could provide

the BU team with high-resolution data from five wells recently installed in the Konya Basin. Then, a protocol of mutual understanding was negotiated between DSI and BU.

Task 3.2: Training and Validation of the Models in the Case Studies

- Castro Verde (Portugal): the project aimed at constructing a model to address the potential impacts of the nearby mining activities from the Neves-Corvo mining site and the forecast of post-closure scenarios. This task could not be reached due to the abrupt cessation of the initial agreement to collaborate with the owner of the mining concession that holds all the data. This caused a lack of data to fulfil the initial goals established: the development of a numerical hydrogeological model of the Castro Verde aquifer. The consequences were mitigated by utilising available public information at a larger scale encompassing the Portuguese part of the Guadiana basin.
- Tympaki (Greece): the project aimed at constructing a model for investigating saltwater intrusion, nitrate pollution, and the interaction of engineered nanoparticles and nano-pesticides with soil under different climate scenarios. Deviations from the intended objective were encountered due to insufficient nanoparticle field data, making it unfeasible to train any full or surrogate model. However, lab-scale analyses were performed under WP5.
- Grombalia (Tunisia): the project aimed at constructing a model for evaluating the impact of industrial effluents released in water bodies, the artificial recharge by treated wastewater, and the evolution of chemical and microbiological quality of the groundwater. The lack of sufficient time-series data on the chemical and microbiological quality of both groundwater and surface water presented an obstacle in conducting progress using surrogate models. However, a comprehensive and continuous data collection and monitoring system for water quality is currently being developed across the pilot site (WP5). This can provide a more robust foundation for future studies and analyses.

Task 3.4: Analysis of Different Scenarios

Task 3.4 aimed at the simulation of different future scenarios. Alongside the investigation of the impact of climate change, some specific scenarios were planned for the pilot sites. However, the following scenarios could not be analysed for the reasons already indicated:

- Castro Verde (Portugal): the scenarios included the impacts of mining closure and socio-economic changes.
- Requena-Utiel (Spain): the scenarios included investigating alternative irrigation procedures and buying irrigation rights during drought periods.
- Grombalia (Tunisia): socio-economic changes, implementation of pollution reduction technologies, artificial recharge, use of treated wastewater.
- Tympaki (Greece): understanding soil particle interaction with nanoparticles.

For Castro-Verde, Grombalia and Tympaki, the deviations arise from the same reasons explained above regarding the deviation of Task 3.2. For Requena-Utiel, thanks to the living labs conducted with the stakeholders in Requena on March 4, 2022, it was found that the irrigation procedures in practice were already very efficient (mainly drip irrigation), and it was not clear which alternative procedures could be put in practice. It was also unclear from the living labs that buying irrigation rights could be a viable solution; however, the surrogate models did include the possibility of analysing a reduction in pumping.

Task 6.1: Initial Development and Testing of an Innovative Decision Support System

This task was not accomplished as described in the proposal. Great efforts were made to incorporate the fuzzy character that the tool was intended to have, but, in the end, it was not included in the DSS as originally planned. Initially, a first attempt was made to train a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) that would integrate all the criteria involved in the decision-making process. The training data were the cost-benefit analysis data for the socio-economic evaluation and the data results of the groundwater simulation optimisation model (environmental criterion). This experiment was not successful, although several alternative approaches were used. In parallel with the FIS system, a second attempt was made to incorporate fuzzy characteristics into the DSS tool as an alternative option. This approach was the “Bound and Decomposition Method” (Jayalakshmi and Pandian, 2012¹¹) in conjunction with the piecewise linear groundwater optimisation approach. The method was applied to the

¹¹ M.Jayalakshmi, P. Pandian, A New Method for Finding an Optimal Fuzzy Solution for Fully Fuzzy Linear Programming Problems, International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA) ISSN: 2248-9622 www.ijera.com Vol. 2, Issue 4, July-August 2012, pp.247-254

optimisation problem for the environmental criterion, but the results were not encouraging. In particular, the algorithm could not provide a final solution to the problem. The approach that was finally adopted is the one presented in Deliverable D6.1 v.2. Since the piezometric head is the parameter that appears in the analyses of all the study sites, the fuzzy clustering method was applied to the results of the smart models, i.e., to the values of the piezometric head. The algorithm accepts the simulated results of two different scenarios as inputs, and the fuzzy clustering method classifies the variations in the groundwater level.

Task 6.2: Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites Under Future Scenarios

The fact that the fuzzy characteristic could not be incorporated into the optimisation approach led to a different setup for the DSS tool. In this framework, each tool user can define their own scenarios. Therefore, indicative scenarios were analysed, and the results are presented in Deliverable D6.3. On the other hand, as an integrated numerical-model-based method for sustainable groundwater use had already been deployed, the TUC team fully used it and analyzed twelve different climate projection scenarios. The results are presented in Deliverable D6.2. Although this approach could not be compiled into the fuzzy web DSS tool, it composes an integrated method for sustainable groundwater use that considers social, economic and environmental criteria.

3.2. Use of Resources

In the case of the UPV team, since HRMS were not installed, the resources allocated to this task were assigned to pay the contracted researchers' salaries during the project extension.

The BU team initially requested 2000 Euro as a subcontracting budget in case a subsidiary in Konya was needed to mediate the processes of stakeholder involvement, focus group meetings and workshops. However, the BU team was sufficiently large and active to do the job by themselves; therefore, this amount was merged with the existing direct costs. Additionally, the allocation for the purchase of HRMS was used to hire a graduate assistant who worked on the collaborative phase of model building.

The IST-ID team initially requested funds to install the HRMS in the case study. As these sensors were not installed, the resources were allocated to fund fellowships that developed the

additional work produced with the TUC and UNIPR teams, which was not initially planned, and to acquire hardware to update the server where the website is hosted.

During the first half of the project, the TUC team transferred an amount of 3,000 Euros from the category “Other direct costs – Travel” to the category “Other direct costs – Other goods & services”. Due to travel restrictions and working conditions resulting from the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the TUC team needed to purchase computer accessories and parts that enabled the staff team to run the necessary software on the office computers remotely and to coordinate remotely.

The number of person-months committed by each partner team for the third reporting period (from March 1, 2020, to August 31, 2023) is listed in Table 3. It is necessary to remark that the actual total PM exceeds the total PM of the proposal due to the 6-month extension that InTheMED was granted.

The UPV team has exceeded the person-months estimated in the proposal for most of the work packages. As the Project Coordinator, the project management has involved more work hours than estimated, and the six-month extension in the project's duration must also be considered. Apart from project management, the UPV team was focused on modelling; therefore, much effort was put into achieving a reliable smart model and its integration into the DSS. Also, more effort than anticipated was dedicated to communication and dissemination. The increase in the person-months has not implied any additional cost.

For the UFZ team, person-months for WPs 1, 2, 4 and 7 were almost used as planned. In WPs 3, 5 and 6, person-months were slightly reduced compared to planned levels. The work of the UFZ team was mainly focused on WP2 and WP7, dealing with historical groundwater level data collection and analyses and project results dissemination. Overall, the UFZ declared only 23.4 PM in reporting periods M1-18 (8.45 PM) and M19-36 (14.95 PM) instead of 28.13 PM (Planned PM according to the Grant Agreement). An assistant student (who was supposed to occupy 4.73 PMs) was not hired to support the team. Instead, more efforts were dedicated to dissemination, publication and outreach activities.

For the UNIPR team, the person-months for WPs 1, 4 and 5 complied with the predicted values of the project. WP2 required more time to process the data pertaining to the Portuguese and

Tunisian sites. WP3, Task 3.4, “Analysis of different scenarios”, required an increase in person-months due to the definition of the scenarios of interest for the individual sites. A similar increase was necessary for the activities needed in WP6 for the definition and refinement of the surrogate models to be optimally inserted into the DSS developed by TUC. Finally, it was necessary to increase the person-months for editing papers for scientific journals and abstracts for communications at scientific conferences and congresses (WP7).

The BU team completed the WPs 1, 2, 5, 6 and 7 tasks within the person-months specified in the proposal. The tasks of WP3 (development of a hydrogeologic model, training of the smart modelling) and WP4 (mapping of stakeholders and calibration of the system dynamics model) took longer effort than anticipated, partly due to the extension of the project duration. The extra person-months needed to complete these tasks were covered by the savings in subcontracting costs and the purchase of the high-resolution sensors.

The CERTE Team successfully managed to stay within the planned person-months for WPs 2, 3, 4, 6, and 7. However, for WP1 and WP5, the person-months exceeded what was estimated. Notably, the CERTE team leads WP5, and this is where the higher number of working hours occurred. The additional effort was invested to ensure the successful achievement of WP5's objectives while adhering to the allocated budget for personnel costs. Furthermore, the team dedicated significant time and effort to WP1. They engaged various members for administrative and financial responsibilities, which were not originally anticipated.

For the TUC team, the person-months for WP1 were used as planned. In WP2, WP3 and WP6, person-months slightly exceeded the planned amount. The work of the TUC team was mainly focused on WP6 and WP3, and many master students worked on the respective tasks. Their salary was not allowed to exceed a certain threshold set by the TUC Finance Office based on internal regulations, resulting in higher person-months than expected. The person-months allocated for WPs 4, 5 and 7 were not fully utilised. The realisation of Living Labs was not foreseen for the Greek site. Therefore, the engagement of stakeholders from the broader audience was weaker, and the dissemination actions of the TUC team were limited to scientific events and interactions with public authorities. Thus, fewer resources were allocated for the tasks of WP4 and WP7. In addition, as for the Greek site, there were no available data for

pollution from nanoparticles and hotspots were not identified; therefore, the resources allocated for WP5 were also reduced.

For the IST-ID team, the predicted and actual total PM is similar. While WPs 1, 2, 3 and 7 exceed the number of planned resources, this fact was compensated by the use of smaller resources in WPs 4, 5 and 6. The increase in resources is due to the extra activities that were not planned in the original proposal (e.g., the monitoring systems for the sandbox with the UNIPR team, the deep learning ERT inversion and the geo-modelling workflow in the Greek aquifer) but are being developed under the scope of the project. These activities are in line with the proposed objectives of the project. The use of fewer resources than expected in WPs 4, 5 and 6 is mainly due to the lack of communication with the owner of the mining site of the Portuguese case study.

Table 3. Summary of staff effort for the third reporting period compared to the proposal (42 months)

		WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total PM
UPV	Proposal	11.65	4	17	3	1	4	5.23	45.88
	Actual	24.5	4.2	30.7	3.5	3.2	7.3	9.5	82.9
UFZ	Proposal	2.5	15.13	2.5	1	2.5	1.5	3	28.13
	Actual	2	15	1	1	1	1	2.4	23.4
UNIPR	Proposal	3.3	4.6	29.2	1.2	1.4	1.0	3.3	44.0
	Actual	3.66	4.97	32.33	1.30	1.4	2.01	4.28	49.93
BU	Proposal	3	4	21	39	5	4	5	81
	Actual								
CERTE	Proposal	2.5	5.0	2.0	4.0	30.0	1.5	2	47
	Actual	9	3.3	0.6	0.5	30.7	0	1.4	45.6
TUC	Proposal	2.46	3	22.9	1.97	5.97	29.4	5.25	70.95
	Actual	2.46	3.52	23.29	1.77	4.05	29.44	4.73	69.26
IST-ID	Proposal	2.73	15.37	2.82	2.34	5.60	5	11.73	45.49
	Actual	2	20.20	5.72	0.5	1	1	17.00	47.42